

The effect of an atypical antipsychotic as part of eradication therapy on the state of the nervous system in patients with peptic ulcer disease associated with Hp and autonomic therapy syndrome

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Purpose of work: to study the effect of an atypical antipsychotic in eradication therapy on patients with peptic ulcer disease associated with Hp and autonomic therapy syndrome in order to select the optimal treatment strategy.

Materials and methods: In the scientific work, 90 patients with peptic ulcer disease associated with *Helicobacter pylori* (Hp) and vegetative dystonia syndrome were selected. All patients were divided into 3 groups: Group I (main) - patients taking an atypical antipsychotic (sulpiride) in combination with quadruple therapy; Group II (comparative) - patients taking an antidepressant (amitriptyline) in combination with quadruple therapy; Group III (control) - patients who exclusively received quadruple therapy. The C14 urease breath test was used to determine the presence of the ulcerative pathogen Hp. In order to determine the presence of an ulcerative defect, the traditional FGDS method was used and the Sakita-Miwa classification was used to determine the condition of the ulcer. The status of the autonomic nervous system was determined using the Spielberger test.

Results of research: Main group (before treatment): 1. Personal anxiety - the average score before treatment was 63.5 points, which indicates a very high level of anxiety in n = 29 patients. 2. Reactive anxiety - the average score before treatment was 44.7 points, which indicates a very high level of anxiety in n = 21 patients..

It should be noted that some patients had both reactive and personal anxiety in all study groups.

Comparison group (before treatment): 1. Personal anxiety - the average score before treatment was 58.8 points, which indicates a very high level of anxiety in n = 31 patients. 2. Reactive anxiety - the average score before treatment was 37.4 points, which indicates a very high level of anxiety n = 23 patients.

Control group (before treatment): 1. Personal anxiety - the average score before treatment was 68.1 points, which indicates a very high level of anxiety in n = 5 patients. 2. Reactive anxiety - the average score before treatment was 40.2 points, which indicates a very high level of anxiety in n = 6 patients. Indicators of the Spielberger test after therapy (in points)

Groups	Personality anxiety	Reactive anxiety
I	13.4	18.2
II	32.4	29.2
III	52.3	38.5

As the survey data show, patients in the main group who received an atypical antipsychotic have a strong shift towards correcting the state of the autonomic nervous system.

Conclusions: Thus, taking into account the results of the study, we can say that there is a significant shift towards improvement in health in patients who took it in combination with sulpiride, since the indicators of the state of the autonomic nervous system, carried out on the basis of a questionnaire and a functional test, improved, an indicator of the stage of ulcer healing in relation to comparative and control group.

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